

Synthesis of some New Pyrazole and Isoxazole Derivatives of Sulphonamides

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Since the last five decades pyrazole ring has attracted much attention as dyes and drugs. A number of pyrazole derivatives have been synthesised as potential antibiotics, antidiabetics, antineoplastics, bacteriostatics, fungicidals and bacteriocidals¹. Steroidal compounds whose structures include pyrazole rings are of interest as possible psychopharmacological agents². Pyrimidinopyrazoles have been studied in the fight against cancer³. Synthesis of model systems analogous to histamine led to the pharmacologically interesting aminoethylpyrazoles⁴. Likewise, compounds having azo/hydrazono groups have exhibited a variety of biological activities⁵. Sulphonamides are of much importance in chemotherapy⁶. A series of azo dyes⁷ have been synthesised by diazotising sulphonamides and coupling with monopolyphenols with or without amino or alkyl groups. Isoxazoles are well known for their medicinal properties⁸. 3,5-Dimethylisoxazole⁹ is a potential hypoglycemic agent. Keeping in view the important biological activities displayed by sulphonamides, pyrazole/isoxazole and azo group, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise some azo derivatives of sulphonamides having pyrazole/isoxazole moiety.

Azopyrazoles and azoisoxazoles of sulphonamides have been synthesised in two stages (Scheme 1). In the first stage, the sulphonamoyl hydrazones (1a-f) were synthesised smoothly by the coupling of sulphonamides with 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione. In the second stage, these were reacted with phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine hydrochloride separately to produce azopyrazoles (2a-f) and azoisoxazoles (3a-f) respectively, in good yields. The structures of these compounds were established on the basis of elemental and spectral analyses.

Scheme 1

For hydrazones the following two structures (I, II) are possible :

Ar = $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-}(p)\text{-SO}_2\text{NHR}$

R = As shown in Scheme

From the adsorption band at 1680 cm^{-1} , observed for
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the carbonyl group of **1a**, it was evident that the carbonyl was hydrogen bonded. In nmr studies of phenylhydrazone¹⁰, the chemical shifts for NH groups have proved to be a sensitive indicator for the presence of hydrogen bonding. The extremely downfield chemical shift of δ 12.70 observed strongly suggested structure (I) for **1a**, hence for the rest of the hydrazones as well.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrometer and nmr spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Varian spectrometer (270 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard. Compounds were routinely checked for their purity on silica gel G plates. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

1-Phenyl-3,5-diphenyl-4-sulphonamoylazopyrazole (2): The starting sulphonamide (R = H; 0.01 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of concentrated HCl (5 ml) and water (5 ml), and cooled to 0° in an ice-bath. Cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.69 g) was then added to it and the diazonium salt so formed was filtered into a cooled solution of sodium acetate (8 g) and 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml). After 15 min, the resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to furnish **1a** (70%), m.p. 135° (Found : C, 62.10; H, 4.00; N, 10.12. $C_{21}H_{17}N_3O_4S$ calcd. for : C, 61.90; H, 4.07; N, 10.31%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 300 (SO_2NH_2), 3 240 (NH), 1 680 (CO), 1 140 (SO_2), 1 530 (NH=N=C) and 750, 1 770 cm^{-1} (substituted phenyl); δ 3.4 (2H, NH_2), 7.0–8.2 (14H, ArH) and 12.70 (1H, NH). Similarly other substituted sulphonamoyl hydrazones were prepared : **1b** (75%), m.p. 183°; **1c** (70%), 165°; **1d** (75%), 120°; **1e** (65%), 185°; **1f** (50%), 60°.

To 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione-2-sulphonamoylhydrazone (**1a**; 0.001 mol) in acetic acid (10–15 ml), a solution of phenylhydrazine (0.001 mol) in acetic acid (15 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h and then allowed to cool overnight. The resulting solid (**2a**) was crystallised from ethanol (65%), m.p. 192° (Found : C, 64.17; H, 4.30; N, 16.92,

$C_{27}H_{21}N_5O_2S$ calcd. for : C, 64.84; H, 4.39; N, 17.45%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 260 (NH), 1 620 (C=C or C=N), 1 510 (N=N), 1 130 (SO_2) and 750 cm^{-1} (phenyl); δ 3.1 (2H, NH_2) and 7.1–8.2 (19H, ArH). Similarly other azopyrazoles were prepared : **2b** (55%), m.p. 72°; **2c** (50%), 85°; **2d** (65%), 125°; **2e** (50%), 115°; **2f** (40%), 132°.

3,5-Diphenyl-4-sulphonamoylazoisoxazole (3): To 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione-2-sulphonamoylhydrazone (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml), a solution of sodium acetate (1 g) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.01 mol) in water was added and the solution was refluxed for 4 h. The mixture was then allowed to cool overnight and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol (50%), m.p. 225° (Found : C, 62.00; H, 3.75; N, 13.54. $C_{21}H_{16}O_3N_4S$ calcd. for : C, 62.36; H, 3.98; N, 13.85%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 500 (N=N), 1 650 (C=C or C=N) and 830, 700 cm^{-1} (substituted phenyl); δ (DMSO- d_6) 3.2 (2H, NH_2) and 7.0–8.0 (14H, substituted phenyl). Similarly other azoisoxazoles were prepared : **3b** (65%), m.p. 230°; **3c** (70%), 195°; **3d** (60%), 170°; **3a** (50%), 210°; **3f** (55%), 70°.

Antibacterial activity : Compounds **2** and **3** were screened *in vitro* against *Bacillus pumilus*, *Pseudomonas mongiferae*, *Vibrio cholerae*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus pyrogenus*. The antibacterial activity of the compounds was tested by the cup-plate technique¹¹ in the concentrating range 0.5–1.0 $mg\ cm^{-3}$. The following compounds showed significant antibacterial activity (zone of inhibition, mm, in parenthesis); **2b** (10–15 mm against *B. pumilus*, *P. mongiferae* and *S. pyrogenus*), **2d** (12–16 mm against *B. pumilus*, *P. mongiferae* and *S. pyrogenus*), **3b** (8–14 mm against *B. pumilus*, *P. mongiferae* and *S. pyrogenus*), **3d** (10–16 mm against *B. pumilus*, *P. mongiferae* and *S. pyrogenus*), **3e** (12–17 mm against *B. pumilus*, *P. mongiferae* and *S. pyrogenus*), **2e** (12 and 16 mm against *B. pumilus* and *V. cholerae*), **2f** (10 and 15 mm against *B. pumilus* and *V. cholerae*), **3c** (14 and 16 mm against *B. pumilus* and *V. cholerae*), **3f** (10 and 17 mm against *B. pumilus* and *V. cholerae*). The standard drug sulphamethoxazole (27–32 mm against the bacteria selected) was used as the control.

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